

A Competitive Aggression And Anxiety Among Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players

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CHAPTER-1 INTRODUCTION

We all know that sports are highly specialized activity and today it has become highly competitive. It has become one of the most widely practiced human activities. Sports are also psycho-social activities, which have a very important role in shaping modern society. The world of games and sports has crossed many milestones. Scientific theories applied to human performance have been playing an increasingly important role in training of athletes to attain excellence in sports and games. Sports performance is the result and expression of the total personality of the sportsman. While some may deride sports psychology as mumbo jumbo, when properly practiced, mental training for sports supplies concrete benefits. Pre-practicing specific routines you'll use during a match or game can help trigger better motor responses and prevent fatigue, among other benefits. One benefit of sport psychology training is that it enhances performance on the court. Winning is one of the main objectives in tennis, but winning requires consistent performance at a high level. Mental proficiency helps ensure this consistency, guarding against fluctuations in performance. As the game becomes more sophisticated, coaches who fail to properly utilize psychological tools place their players, and themselves, at a disadvantage in performance and satisfaction. A full investment in sport psychology may spell the difference between high achievement and mediocrity for players. For years sport psychologists have examined how psychological skills training, including mental skills training, help athletes improve performance. Mental skills Are procedures that help athletes control their minds efficiently and consistently as they execute sport-related goal. This not only involves developing skills such as concentration and stress control, but it also includes efforts to influence personal characteristics such as self-esteem and sportsmanship.

Psychological skills techniques help athletes make adjustments to their actions, thoughts, feelings, and physical sensations that will improve their games. Players can use these techniques to

- help build self-confidence,
- set goals,
- manage their stress,

- use imagery and visualization to work on game skills,
- Focus concentration and attention.

Sport psychology also can help athletes with problems off the court that may affect performance on court.

Mental Game Coaching is the segment of sports psychology that concentrates specifically on helping athletes break through the mental barriers that are keeping them from performing up to their peak potential. By focusing on the mental skills needed to be successful in any sporting competition, mental game coaching seeks to achieve the overall goal of performance improvement.

Sports Psychology is about improving your attitude and mental game skills to help you perform your best by identifying limiting beliefs and embracing a healthier philosophy about your sport.

Psychological makeup of the sportsman takes a leading role on top level performance in any competition. Psychological factors determine the competitive behavior, mental processes and preparation before competition. Sports psychology deals with increasing performance by managing emotions and minimizing the psychological factors that deteriorate performance. Some of the most important psychological skills that are taught to athletes are goal setting, relaxation, visualization, self-talk, awareness and control, concentration using rituals, and attribution. It has been recognized for many years that psychological factors, in particular Anxiety and Aggression, play a crucial role in competition (Lizuka, C.A etal., 2005).

Anxiety is an emotion characterized by feelings of tension, worried thoughts and physical changes like increased blood pressure. People with anxiety disorders usually have recurring intrusive thoughts or concerns. They may avoid certain situations out of worry.

components. The root meaning of the anxiety is "to trouble" in either the absence or presence of psychological stress. it can create feelings of fear, worry and uneasiness. It is also defined as a disturbed state of the body, emotional reactivity, nervousness, unpleasant state of the body and mind. Physical effects of anxiety may include heart palpitation. muscle weakness, tension, fatigue, chest pain, shortness of breath, stomach-aches and headaches. The body prepares to deal with threat by increasing blood pressure and heart rate, sweating, blood flow to the major muscle groups. Visual manifestations of anxiety may include pale skin, sweating and trembling Performance anxiety is not uncommon in sports, as to some extent, fear of performance helps in achieving desired concentration. However, the excess will lead to a rush of adrenaline termed as anxiety. Whenever

you feel short of breath, sweating, shaking or high heart beat rate. You lose concentration, your actions become disjointed and you feel paralyzed at the beginning of an important sporting event. These are symptoms of performance anxiety. You no longer feel confident in yourself and do not believe that you will be able to accomplish anything successful. To deal with such thoughts you must learn how to manage anxiety and to do so, it is imperative to understand how sports performance and anxiety are interrelated.

Anxiety affects a sports players' performance in physiological, cognitive and behavioral ways. If you suffer from anxiety before an important athletic competition, your sports performance will be affected. When your body is tense and blood pressure high, it is difficult for your body to move in a fluid and coordinated manner. Your actions will be jerky and misplaced, affecting your performance in a negative manner. Listed below are the ways in which anxiety can affect sports performance.

1. Fear

When you are afraid of a certain situation, you may experience body paralysis once you find yourself present in that situation. This indicates severe anxiety. An example of this is when an athlete suffers from stage fright, which they may experience right before a large, public competition. When feeling overwhelming fear, the athlete may be unable to move, talk or act at all.

2. Unable to Concentrate

Pre-competitive anxiety also develops as an inability to concentrate before an upcoming event or competition. The athlete is unable to concentrate on the task at hand and therefore cannot give their performance full attention. The root cause of the inability to concentrate is feelings of apprehension.

Apprehensions cause the individual to feel that they will fail or decrease their confidence in their ability. These negative thoughts will invade the individual's mind and cause them to lose concentration, which results in mixing up tasks and forgetting what is needed to be done in the present situation.

3. Sweating

The anxiety makes the athlete over conscious of his situation and the apprehensions make him feel uneasy. As a result, the body may feel sudden bursts of heat and will release a lot of perspiration when the body receives signals from the brain. Excessive sweating can occur anywhere on the body mainly on the hands and the face. The individual will begin to feel uncomfortable and this merely reinforces the anxiety they are already feeling.

4. Racing Heart

As a result of anxiety the heart rate of an athlete may also increase manifold. This may be due to the excessive release of adrenaline in the body. Increased heart rates are also related to panic. If the athletes become increasingly panicked, the heart rate will also increase.

5. Shortness of Breath

Breathing very fast or panting is another symptom of anxiety. Sometimes the athletes experience a shortness of breath and struggle to take in oxygen. It is not uncommon for athletes to hyperventilate due to severe anxiety. This in turn can deprive the brain of enough oxygen, which would lead to dizziness and/or fainting.

6. Dizziness

When an athlete is suffering from severe anxiety and is panicking, the brain may not receive as much blood and oxygen as it normally does. This results in dizziness, which if severe can result in the athlete fainting. Feelings of dizziness can disable the athlete to such an extent that they may be unable to perform.

7. Shaking

Before a competition or important event, an athlete may experience severe shaking of the hands or knees. This is due to an increased spike of adrenaline in the body, which is brought on by severe anxiety. If the anxiety persists, the body may collapse.

Anxiety is divided into two types, 'State and Trait anxiety'. Trait anxiety is personality trait. It is influenced by heredity and nothing much can be done to change the trait anxiety. State anxiety on the other hand can be controlled and altered. It changes according to the situation. State anxiety is further subdivided into two sub components such as, 'Cognitive and Somatic Anxiety'. Cognitive anxiety is characterized by negative thoughts, inability to concentrate and disturbed attention. Somatic anxiety is one's perception of psychological arousal such as rapid heart rate, tensed muscles and butterflies in stomach. Somatic anxiety differs from psychological arousal in that arousal is measured through actual physiological indicators: (such as increased blood pressure, increased pulse rate etc.), while somatic anxiety reflects one's perception of their psychological arousal. It is important to distinguish cognitive anxiety from somatic anxiety. Anxiety has been proposed to differentially relate to athletic performance and has different antecedents. Cognitive anxiety is expected to negatively affect athletic performance while somatic anxiety will have a curvilinear relationship with performance.

Aggression is one amongst the psychological fitness. Aggression defined as the energetic assault on animate or inanimate objects for a purpose. Aggression is always associated by some negative emotional state. The emotion which is called as anger is usually aroused by some provocation (Alderman, 1974). The word aggression comes from the Latin word *aggres*, 'ad' (to or toward) and *grader* (walk). Literally then the word means to "to walk towards or approach", to move against or to move with intent to hurt or harm. Most psychologists describe aggression in terms of behavior. Aggressive behavior is associated with destructive acts, sexual attacks, prejudiced, speeches, genital activities, drug and alcohol addictions, sports and exercise' crying' complaining, waging wars and so forth.

Sports psychologists distinguished two types of aggression in sport, first one is hostile and second one is instrumental (Grange, & Kerr, 2010). In hostile aggression a participant purposely tries to harm his/her opponent physically. Instrumental aggression is used to achieve certain goal. It can be to tackle harder to gain possession of the ball in (ice) hockey (Jones, Bray, & Olivier, 2005). It is also known as channeled aggression, this is because an individual has the ability to turn it on & off and control their temperament, which is not associated with anger (Berkowitz, 1962; Katko, Meyer, Mihura, & Bombel, 2010).

Most aggression in sport results from frustration. This frustration is the result of various motives being blocked, which are predominant in sport and generate aggression. The sublime form of aggression revolves around achievement, dominance, power, recognition, prestige and excellence.

If a boy places high incentive value on one or a combination of these motives and the incentive systems are blocked from attaining or satisfying them, he becomes frustrated. In essence aggression is primarily a learned behavior, which is the result of an individual's interaction with his or her social environment over time. Aggression occurs in sports, where an athlete's generalized expectancies for the reinforcement for aggressive behavior are high (e.g.: receiving praise from parents, coaches, peers) and where the reward value outweighs punishment value (e.g.: gaining a tactical and psychological advantage with a personal foul in basketball, a yardage penalty in American Football). This is deemed an appropriate time to exhibit aggression.

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of the study is to find competitive aggression and anxiety among kabaddi and kho-kho players.

Statement of the problem:

Is aggression and anxiety significantly differ amongst kabaddi and Kho-kho players?

Hypothesis:

1. There will be significant difference in aggression among kabaddi and kho-kho sports players.
2. There will be significant difference in anxiety among kabaddi and kho-kho sports players.

LIMITATION:

The limitation of the present study is as follow

1. Environmental factors, which contribute to the mental ability of the players, were not taken into consideration.
2. The response of the subject to the questionnaire might not be honest in all cases and this was recognized as a limitation.

DELIMITATIONS:

The present study was delimited in the following aspects.

- 1) The study was restricted to 50 kabaddi and kho-kho players.
- 2) The age limit of the subjects was 18-25
- 3) The study was restricted to the aggression and anxiety.
- 4) Only standardized questionnaire was used to measure the psychological variables.
- 5) Only boys were considered as samples for study.
- 6) Only Belagavi district students are considered as sample for the study.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study was to investigate the existing difference between kabaddi and kho kho players in relation to their aggression and kho-kho.

- The finding of the study may provide guidance to the physical education teachers and coaches to prepare training programmes on the basis of the study.
- It may further help the researchers who are interested in kabaddi and kho-kho players
- The finding of the study may add to the quantum of knowledge in the area of sports and physical education.

Definition of terms

The research was to find the level of aggression and anxiety between kabaddi and kho-kho players of during the intercollegiate meet

Kabaddi:

Kabaddi is a contact team sports that originated in India subcontinent in Amravati Maharashtra state. In the modern teams kabaddi was given the national status of a game in India in 1918. The state of Maharashtra is accredited with upbringing the game to a national platform. It is popular in south Asia and is the state game of Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Tamilnadu. Maharashtra, Bihar and Punjab it is also the national sports of Bangladesh.

Two teams compete each occupying its own half of the court. They take turns sending a raider into the opposing team half and earn points if the raider manages to touch opposing team members and return to the home half all while taking only a single breath it however the raider is taken and prevented from returning the opposing team earns the points

Field of play the playground of the kabaddi shall be level and soft preferably made of earth manure and sawdust. The ground shall be 13X10 meter for women 12X8 meter and sub junior girl and boys 11X8 meter The mid line drawn divides the playground into two courts. There shall be strip of one meter wide on each side of the play field which called lobby In each half at a distance of about mid line and parallel to it lines of the full width of ground shall be drawn these are back lines

KHO KHO

Kho-kho is a semi contact game sports organized by Maharashtra at gymkhana Poona: A committee was formed in 1914, to form its rules. In 1959-60 first national kho-kho championship was organized in Vijayawada

Each team consists to 12 players but only 9 players take the field for a contest. A match consists of two innings An innings consists of chasing and running terms of 7 minutes each. 8 members of the chasing team sit in their 8 squares on the central lane, alternately facing the opposite direction, while the 9 member is an active chaser and stands at either of the posts, ready to being the pursuit.

Field A kho-kho playground is rectangular It is 27 meter in length and 16meter width and there are two rectangular at the end 16 meter width and free zone 1.50 meter central lane 30*35 cm box Ground shall be drawn these are side lines

Anxiety:

Anxiety is an emotion characterized by feelings of tension, worried thoughts, and physical changes like increased blood pressure. People with anxiety disorders usually have recurring intrusive thoughts or concerns

Aggression:

aggression is a characteristic that can have many negative as well as positive effects on performance. Aggression is defined as “any form of behaviour directed toward the goal of harming or injuring another live being who is motivated to avoid such treatment”

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In this chapter previously done literature was reviewed according to subject of the study. Findings of previous literature was presented below.

Mahesh Kumar Associate Professor, CKM Jat College, Hisar" His Studied on Aggressive Tendency among the Kabaddi and Kho-Kho Players. This study was carried with an objective to find out the difference of aggression level among the players of Kabaddi and Kho Kho game. In this study used stratified random sampling technique, to select the sample. The present investigation was conducted on 50 sports persons of Haryana state, within the age limit of 15-19 years. Out of total sample of 50 players, 25 were of Kabaddi and 25 of Kho-Kho games. The study showed that the mean value of aggressive behavior of Kabaddi players was higher than that of Kho-Kho players at 0.05 level of significance. So the players of Kabaddi game had more aggressive behavior than that of Kho-Kho players. This may be due to the more body contact of the players in Kabaddi game.

Parthasarathi compared anxiety, stress and achievement motivation of Basketball. Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players." The purpose was to compare the anxiety stress and achievement motivation of Basketball, Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players. Seventy Six Madras University players of Kho-Kho, Basketball and Kabaddi aged between 18 to 25 year were selected as the subject. Spielberg' Questionnaires was adopted to find out anxiety level. F Ratio was computed to find out the signification. The result of this study showed that there was no significant difference among players of Kho-Kho and Kabaddi.

"Bakian A Palsiaouas A, Kokanidas D. And Sekellariou K have studied the relation studied the relation of verbal aggressiveness and state anxiety (somatic, cognitive and self-confidence) in sport setting based on the relating (N-208, 98men

and 110 women) and their coacher (N=20, 16 men, 4 women). They concluded that male Kho-kho players rated somatic anxiety higher and were more effected by the verbal aggressiveness of their coach than female Kho-Kho players and coach was found. The correlation of verbal aggressiveness with self-confidence and anxiety were positive for these athletes, leading them to better behavior. The relationship needs further examination in sports setting setting.

Shivaramakn'shnanan and Nagaswaran (1998) investigated Psychosocial profile of low and high level achievers of all individual inter University Kabaddi Women teams. Dr. MM. Klmesh sports achievement motivation test questionnaire Marten and Burl ton competition state anxiety inventory-2, correctly adaptation of pies, Harries self-concept scale over used. The purposed of the study was to analyses the similarities and differences in achievement motivation competitive state and trait anxieties, sports man ship and self-concept among inter University Kabaddi women player. To archive the purpose of the study Kabaddi players from various universities who participated in all Inter University Kabaddi, tournament were selected. The age of women Kabaddi players 18-25 years, that ratio was used there was significant difference between low and high achievers in competition state anxiety (self-confidence and cognitive anxiety) sportsmanship and self concept.

Prakash Bandana (2002) studies the relationship between factors influencing sports career and anxiety and self-confidence. For the purpose of the study 72 male players (Athletes-6, Basketball-6, KhoKho-6, Football-S, Hockey-5, Kho-Kho-7, Kho-Kho-7, Kbaddi-7 Kho-Kho6, Combat sports-5, and others-11) were selected and random basis. To collect the required data the inventory of factors influencing sports career (FISC), of Kalmesh and Sharma and llanos self evaluation questionnaire were used, Pearson 'r' was applied for statistical treatment of data. They concluded that internal control factor has significantly and positively related to self-confidence an also having negative relation to adjustment. External control factors influencing the sports career having positive significant relationship adjust.

Thomas Vaughn Walker (1979) conducted a study on Aggression in sport, a study of fouling in University Basketball. The purpose of the study was to determine differences in the occurrence of aggressive actions (fouls) under several conditions. The intent was to examine the possibility of predicting aggressive actions throughout the game. Official's play-by-play Sheets were used to gather the data. The findings of this investigation indicate that fouling is predictable when the range of scoring increases and during the first and last five minutes of the second half. The implications associated with the findings are the following: The frustration of the game situation causes aggressive behavior. No cathartic effect is

a result of displaying aggressive actions. Several factors contribute to the occurrence of fouling behavior in basketball games including accidents, international fouls, coach requested fouls, and over aggressiveness by players.

Gilldiane (1986) purports that some of the psychological review suggests that gender differences exist in the aggressive behavior but gender difference in sports aggression have not been examined. Enterprising investigator has countless issues to examine in relation to gender and individual differences and how they interact with situational factors to influence aggressive behavior.

Baron (1987) suggests that if provocation is low, men are more likely to behave aggressively than women. But under conditions of higher provocation both are likely to react in similar manner.

Sharma (1987) in order to find out relationship between aggression and various dimensions of self-concept of hockey players of various colleges of Punjab University Chandigarh conducted a study by administering Saraswat (SCQ) Nagri's aggression Scale Questionnaires and found that relationship of aggression with social, educational, moral and intellectual dimensions of self-concept is negative but significant statistically. Hockey players possess high level aggression and average level of self-concept on all the dimensions.

In some studies Clarizie, Hanrey F. (1992) several controversies continue to surround the differentiation between the socially maladjusted (SM) and seriously emotionally disturbed (SED) central to the controversy is the interpretation of social maladjustment. At one extreme, some restrict the definition of SM to include the socialized aggressive and adjudicated delinquents. At the other extreme, SM is constructed broadly and includes:

- (1) Conduct disorder (group type solitary aggressiveness)
- (2) Oppositional defiant disorder, and
- (3) Anti social personality.

An intermediate position presented herein argues for the inclusion of the socialized aggressive and unsocialized aggressive under the rubric of S.M. Given that those in the anxious withdrawn dysphonic group are viewed as both SM and SED. They should be eligible for special education services assuming adverse educational impact is evident.

Buss and Perry (1992) found that possible aggression involves physical haran.

Baumgartner(1993) conducted a study on 100 girls and 100 boys (age 16 years) from Slovak high schools to read description of a classroom injury that was

accidental or intentional and were asked to describe the episode and imagine the further possible development of the situation. Girls rated the victimizer's behavior as more inconsiderable and unintelligible than did the boys while boys evaluated the victimizer's behavior in both situations in approximately the same way, girls evaluated the intentional incident as more unintelligible girls also perceived the intentional incident as causing more tension than did boys. As follow up actions, boys considered aggression more appropriate, while girls favored meditation.

Tenenbaum Gershon et al (2000) conducted a study on response to J.H.Kerr's rejoinder to the International society in sport Psychology's Position stand on aggression and violence in sport, this reply refutes Kerr's to drastically reduce aggression among athletes and spectators. Specifically, this paper answers Kerr's accusations that the PS fails to provide an understanding of the motivation behind aggression in sports, improper conclusions regarding the media's influence, and incorrectly blames officials for inflaming aggressive acts. Support is offered to vindicate the PS.

Arnold (2001) found that contact sports such as football and rugby had provoked aggression in all the field.

Cox (2002) studied that possible aggression is more frequent in contact than in no contact sports. Contact sports may attract people who are already aggressive or engaging in contact sports may promote aggression. Cox had also suggested that football players, who are contact sport athletes are more aggressive than no contact athlete such as golfer or tennis players. Elman and McKelvie (2000) also found that university football players has higher narcissism than other athletes, which involves anger and aggressive behavior.

Eric A. Storch, Nicole E. Werner, Jason B. Storch; Journal of Sport Behavior, Vol. 26, (2003) Aggression among athletes has received increasing attention from the media, school administrators, and researchers over the past decade (Humphrey & Kahn, 2000; Kerr, 1999; Rowe, 1998; Tenenbaum, Stewart, Singer, & Duda, 1997). From such reports, important information has been generated regarding the types of aggressive acts engaged in both on and off the field (e.g., instrumental versus hostile), as well as the societal consequences of such behavior (e.g., team dismissal, suspension, negative public image, arrest, etc.). However, two limitations plague the extant literature. First, the majority of past research with athletes has defined aggression in terms of physical or verbal acts, behaviors that are more characteristic of male's aggression than of female's, who are more likely to use relational aggression (Werner & Crick, 1999). Second, although clinical observations have linked physical aggression to emotional difficulties (e.g., depression) and substance use in athletes. (Nicholi, 1987). little

empirical attention has been given to internalizing and externalizing difficulties that may be associated with aggressive behavior in this population. The present pilot study was designed to address these limitations by examining the association between relational aggression and psychosocial adjustment in a sample of intercollegiate athletes.

Kumar, R (2005) had conducted a study to evaluate the impact of mental imagery training on the selected psycho-somatic parameters i.e.. anxiety, sports competition anxiety and aggression as well as on the mental imagery abilities of boxers belonging to the state of Himachal Pradesh. All the subjects had participated in the boxing competition at state level. Kumar found that with regard to the variable aggression, ANOVA results indicated that the four groups had similar pre-experimental states as the F-value was wholly insignificant being .254. The post experimental multivariate result on this variable revealed that in between the four groups, the obtained post-test F value was 6.417 which was found to be significant ($p < 0.01$). These results pointed out significant difference between these four groups. The relaxation group was found to have significantly lower level of aggression as compared to the skill and result imagery group as well as the combined imagery group. The gender difference among the boxers in this variable was not found to be significant, being slightly below the level of significance at 0.05.

Kalpana Sharma, Khalid Azim Khan, Zeeshan Haider, Sartaj Khan(2012)Sports involve extremely complex behavioral issues. As a consequence of intense competition sportsman's behavior may undergo important changes. The aim of the present study was to determine the aggressive behavior in soccer players at different levels of competition. The present study conducted on 300 male soccer players who were divided into three categories according to three different levels i.e. inter-region, intervarsity and all India intervarsity level. Aggression of the players was measured by using Aggression questionnaire of Kumar & Shukla (1988). The results of the study revealed that all India intervarsity players had lower level of aggression and inter-regional players had higher level of aggression amongst the groups.

Ravneet (1995) conducted study on 120 sportsmen/women of post-graduation Kurukshetra University. Among sportsmen/women she took males and females belonging to judo, gymnastics, cricket, badminton and basketball games. She found significant difference in sportswomen and non-sports women where sportswomen were more aggressive. There was no difference in sportsmen and non-sportsmen whereas sportsmen were more aggressive than sportswomen and non sportsmen were found more aggressive than non-sportswomen. The

participants of Judo, Gymnastics were more aggressive than individuals played Cricket, Basketball and Badminton.

B.Sunil Kumar (2009) the aim of the present study was to study the difference in Physical Fitness among Kabbadi and Kho Kho Players in Hyderabad. 15 Male Kabbadi Players and 15 Male Kho Kho Players between the age group of 18 Years to 28 Years were taken for the Study. The AAPHER Youth Fitness Test consisting of 6 Items were used for the Study. It was found that Kho Kho Players have good Physical Fitness compare to the Kabbadi. This study shows that the Kho Kho Players are good because they do good Physical Training compare to Kabbadi Players.. The Kho Kho Players are having very good speed, strength and endurance.

Karad P.L. (2010) the aim of the study was to find out the gender difference in Personality traits of Inter collegiate male and kho-kho players with regard to psychoticism, neuroticism, extraversion and Lie score. For this present study, 50 male and 50 female kho-kho players were selected as a subject The Eysenck Personality Inventory (E.P.I.) was used to measure Psychotics extraversion and neuroticism of kho-kho players, t-ratios has been used to compare the significantly gender difference between male and female kho-kho players who had participated in Inter collegiate kho-kho tournament held at M.I.T. College, Aurangabad 2010. Gender differences on Psychotics was found between male and female A Kho-Kho players ($t =$) where female players more player more psychotic than male.. While analyzing the differences of Personality characteristic of male and female kho-kho players, gender differences on neuroticism was found between male and female Inter collegiate kho-kho players ($t = 4.69, P < .01$), where the male kho-kho players was found to have less score on neuroticism. So far extraversion was concerned, significant gender difference was found to the male and female Inter-Collegiate kho-kho players ($t = 2.77, P < .01$), male kho-kho players has lower extraversion. Hence, female kho-kho players was more extravert.

Minaxi M. Patel (2010) Physical fitness is the condition of ones body judged in term of age, height, weight and chest expansions in term of absence of defects from disease, constitutional affection or bodily infirmity, full physical development, vigour, vitality and radiant health should be seen in one who is physically fit Anxiety is a multi system response to a perceived threat or danger. It reflects a combination of biochemical change in the body, the patient's personal history and memory and the social station. As far as we know anxiety is a uniquely human experience. Although anxiety is a common place experience that everyone has from time to time, it is difficult to describe concretely because it has so many difficult potential causes and degrees of intensity. 40 players of Kho-Kho game, shri experimental school, Patan were selected by purposive sampling method. The

subjects were selected from high school only. Researcher hypothesized that, "subjects with high physical fitness will be having low anxiety. Subjects with low physical fitness will be having high anxiety. Physical fitness of subjects will increase." For measurement of physical fitness, AAHPER physical fitness test was used. For measurement of anxiety SIINHAS COMPREHENSIVE ANXIETY TEST was used. The experimental group was given practical training. There were given training of 10 weeks for development of Kho-Kho game. There was no practical training given to control group. Both the groups had similarly 20 subjects in them. The researcher was collected the data of pre and post test through AAHPER test and SINHA ANXIETY test. After analysis of data, there was increased physical fitness level of subjects of control group. In control group there was no difference between pre and post test.

CHAPTER-3

METHODOLOGY

As discussed earlier the main purpose of the study was to investigate the varying level of competition aggression and anxiety of a team which progress through tournament the secondary purpose of the present investigate is to acquire lato differing level of aggression and anxiety between kabaddi and kho-kho players during tournament.

For the purpose of the study 100 players of college men's kabaddi and kho-kho players. For this study the age limits of the subjects was in the range of 18-25 age.

Table no 1: Sample size for the study

Variable	Kabaddi players	Kho-Kho players
Aggression and Anxiety	50	50

Administration of questionnaire and collection of data

Research scholaur went to different colleges of Belagavi district administered the questionnaire in class room. Initially subject was asked to fullfill the demographic information provided. Then subject was asked to answer all the questions which were given in the questionnaire.

Sports competition anxiety test (SCAT)

As the investigation of anxiety in sports psychology progreed Marti expressed the need for sports specific measures of Anxiety and developed the sports anxiety test (SCAT) to measure competition train anxiety competition was

defined as the tendency to perceive sports situation as their training and to respond to the sensitizations as apprehension and tension martons measure of state anxiety. There will be three options given rarely, sometimes and often. For rarely option 1 point given for sometimes 2 points given and for often option 3 points will be given. For question 1,4,7,10 and 13th question despite of any responses 0 points will be given.

SCAT scores

Less than 17 you have low level of anxiety

17 to 24. you have an average of anxiety

More than 24 you have an a high level of anxiety

Sports competition aggression test

The aggression questionnaire inventory of by Anandkumar and PremShankara was of Kabaddi and kho-kho players the aggression questionnaire inventory of 25 items in which 13 items are keyed YES and 12 items are keyed No consist yes items are 1,4,5,6,9,12,14,16,18,21,22,24, and 25 No items are 2,3,7,8,10,11,13,17,19,20 and 23 Minimum scores for each statement was one score obtained for each statement were added to represents an individual's total score on aggression.

Statistical Analysis.

To find out significant mean difference among kabaddi and kho-kho player's anxiety and aggression independent sample t-test was used. Mean and Sd were calculated. Level of significance was kept to 0.05

CHAPTER-IV DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Introduction:

However valid. Reliable and adequate the data may be, it does not serve any useful purpose unless it is carefully processed. Systematically classified and tabulated, scientifically analyzed, intelligently interpreted and rationally concluded.

After the data been collected, and was processed and tabulated using Microsoft Excel-2013 software and SPSS V .20.0.1 Software. The data collected on aggression and anxiety from and kabaddi and players Intercollegiate level. The aim of the study is to "Study of Aggression and anxiety Level, among kabaddi (Men) and kho-kho (Men) Players of university intercollegiate karnatak university players. Then the data were analyzed with reference to the objectives and hypotheses by using independent sample 't' test with respect to aggression and

anxiety. The statistical significance was set at 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$) and the results obtained thereby have been interpreted.

AGGRESSION

Table no. 2: Mean, Standaerd deviation an independentsample t-test table of Aggression among kabaddi and kho-kho.

	Mean	Sd	T	Df	Sig
Kabaddi	8.26	3.35	-1.723	98	0.088
Kho-Kho	9.34	2.89			

From the above Independent sample t-test variable we may observe that kho kho players mean aggression is greater than kabaddi players. To verify whether mean difference between two groups is significantly deferent further date is subjected to independent sample t test when we observe obtained t- value in the table i.e. -1.723 is less than the critical t -value 1.98 for 98 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Hence we may conclude that aggression among kabaddi and kho kho players is not significantly different. Mean and standard deviation in the form of graph is expressed below in the figure No.1 Graph

Figure No.1: Bar chart of aggression among kabaddi and kho-kho players.

ANXIETY

Tableno. 3: Mean, Standaerd deviation an independentsample t-test table of Anxiety among kabaddi and kho-kho.

	Mean	Sd	T	Df	Sig
Kabaddi	20.52	2.17	1.363	98	0.176
Kho-Kho	19.74	3.40			

From the above Independent sample t-test variable we may observe that kabaddi players mean anxiety score is greater than kho kho players. To verify whether mean difference between two groups is significantly deferent further date is subjected to independent sample t test when we observe obtained t- value in the table i.e.1.363 is less than the critical t -value 1.98 for 98 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Hence we may conclude that anxietyamong kabaddi and kho kho players is not significantly different. Mean and standard deviation in the form of graph is expressed below in the figure No.2 Graph

Figure No.2: Bar chart of Anxiety among kabaddi and kho-kho players.

Discussion:

From the result of the study we can observe that Anxiety and Aggression doesn't significantly differ among sports Men and non sportsmen. All the samples for the

study are belongs to same regional area and same age group. There experience of playing game is also same. So this might influenced on the result. Kabaddi and Kho-Kho both are indigenous games. Elements of psychological factors are same on both the games. So this may be influenced on the result of the study.

CHAPTER-V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

SUMMARY

The Purpose of the study was to find out the aggression and anxiety level of Kabaddi and kho-kho players.

In order of achieve the purpose of the study 60 selected men who are kabaddi and kho-kho players were selected.

To assess the level of aggression (inventory) and anxiety (SCAT) questionnaire was used to compare data from selected subjects.

Then the data analyzed with reference to the objectives and hypotheses by using independent in aggression and anxiety level among Kabaddi and kho-kho players were using SPSS V: 20.0.1 statistical software and the results obtained thereby have been interpreted.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the analysis the researchers is confident of arriving at certain conclusions based of the results of the study they are as followed.

1. The intercollegiate university level kabaddi and kho-kho players are didn't significantly differ in their aggression.
2. The intercollegiate university level kho-kho and kabaddi players didn't significantly differ in their anxiety.

Recommendations:

While conducting this study the research felt certain related avenues for further research.

1. The similar study may be conducted on inter university Kabaddi and kho-kho university players.
2. Similar study can be conducted other games.
3. It was recommended to apply their study for their University sportsmen. state level, National level sportsmen also.

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APPENDIX-I

SPORTS COMPETITION ANXIETY TEST

Assess how you feel about the following situation when you compete in sports and all games, using the following scale.

Name of the player	
Sex	
Name of the University and college	
Place	
Date of Birth	
No of years participating	

Si No	Questionnaire	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
1	Competing against Other is Socially enjoyable.			
2	Before I Compete, I Feel Uneasy .			
3	Before I Compete, I worry about not performing well.			
4	I am a sport person when I compete.			
5	When I compete, I worry about making mistakes.			
6	Before I compete, I worry about making mistakes.			
7	Setting a goal is important while completing.			
8	Before I compete I get as queasy feeling in my stomach.			
9	Just before competing, I notice that my heart beat faster than usual.			
10	I like to compete in games that demand considerable physical energy.			
11	Before I compete I Feel relaxed.			
12	Before I compete I Feel nervous.			
13	Team sports are more exciting than individual sports.			
14	I get nervous when start the game.			
15	Before I compete I usually get upset.			

APPENDIX-II**Aggression Questionnaire**

Questionnaire	YES	NO
1. I believe in aggressive playing.	()	()
2. I never loose temper while playing.	()	()
3. I never loose temper even if spectator hoots at me.	()	()
4. Tbecome angry while I find myself loosing.	()	()
5. I am extremely imitated on unfair decisions.	()	()
6. I like excitement in game.	()	()
7. I play for fun.	()	()
8 I never feel excited even when opponent is aggressive.	()	()
9. I try to hurt the opponent to deprive him from winning.	()	()
10.I always accept all the decisions of the Referee.	()	()
11.I never feel angry while playing.	()	()
12.I forget everything in anger.	()	()
13.I feel sad if the opponent is injured.	()	()
14.I do not hesitate to win the game through brawl.	()	()
15.Good performance of the opponent gladdens me.	()	()
16.I do not hesitate to inflict utmost harm to the opponent.	()	()
17. Winning or loosing a game is not important to me.	()	()
18.I get pleasure in harassing the opponent.	()	()
10.I am not easily annoyed.	()	()
20.I feel a player must be penalized for inappropriate violence .	()	()
21.I am not worried to see my opponent burt and scream.	()	()
22.I find myself full of aggression during sports.	()	()
23.I dislike winning a game by unfair means.	()	()
24.I can go out of the way to win a game.	()	()
25.When an opponent does me a wrong I try to pay him back.	()	()

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